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Serum β -endorphin levels is associated with the addiction to suicidal behavior: a pilot study.

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Abstract:	<p>The literature provides partial support to the hypothesis that some suicide attempters develop a behavioral addiction to suicidal behavior (SB). We hypothesized that major suicide repeaters (MR) (≥ 5 lifetime suicide attempts) are addicted to suicide attempts as measured with a modified DSM-IV criteria for substance dependence. In this cross-sectional study with 13 psychiatric controls (PC), 55 non-major suicide attempters (NMR), and 9 MR we found that MR are characterized by emotional abuse and neglect, and higher scores using the S-PLE scale. The levels of 8 AM serum ACTH, cortisol and β-endorphin were elevated in all three groups. Serum β-endorphin (pg/mL) was particularly high in PC diagnosed with schizophrenia 220.34 (± 56.30). The level of 8 AM serum β-endorphin raised with an increasing number of criteria for the addiction to SB from 130.31 (± 88.16) (≥ 3 criteria of addiction to SB) to 174.84 (± 114.93) (≥ 6 criteria of addiction to SB) whereas serum ACTH and cortisol did not change. Addicts to SB (≥ 6 criteria) displayed higher serum β-endorphin concentrations than non-addicts (174.84 \pm 114.93 vs. 116.93 \pm 61.70, FET $p=0.09$). The present study brings some support to the addictive hypothesis of SB. Our results delineate β-endorphin as a promising biomarker of the addiction to SB, and offer a good basis for future studies testing if buprenorphine can be used to prevent repetitive suicide attempts and non-suicidal-self-injury (NSSI), and the development of an addiction to SB.</p>
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Cover letter

Madrid, 31st December, 2019

Dear Editor,

On behalf of my colleagues I would like to submit to *European Neuropsychopharmacology* the full length research clinical research paper entitled ***Serum β -endorphin levels is associated with the addiction to suicidal behavior: a pilot study.***

The present study brings some support to the addictive hypothesis of suicidal behavior. The level of 8 AM serum β -endorphin raised with an increasing number of criteria for the addiction to SB from 130.31 (\pm 88.16) (\geq 3 criteria of addiction to SB) to 174.84 (\pm 114.93) (\geq 6 criteria of addiction to SB) whereas serum ACTH and cortisol did not change. Addicts to SB (\geq 6 criteria) displayed higher serum β -endorphin concentrations than non-addicts (174.84 \pm 114.93 vs. 116.93 \pm 61.70, FET $p=0.09$). Our results delineate β -endorphin as a promising biomarker of the addiction to SB, and offer a good basis for future studies testing if buprenorphine can be used to prevent repetitive suicide attempts and non-suicidal-self-injury (NSSI), and the development of an addiction to SB.

The manuscript represents original material, has not been previously published, and is not under consideration for publication elsewhere. The manuscript has been read and approved by all authors. All authors authors have contributed to preparing the manuscript and no person or persons other than the authors listed have contributed significantly to its preparation.

If you need any further information please do not hesitate to contact us.

Yours sincerely,

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HIGHLIGHTS β -endorphin

- Addicts to suicidal behavior have higher serum β -endorphin concentrations than non-addicts
- Serum β -endorphin was particularly high in controls with schizophrenia
- Serum β -endorphin was particularly low in controls with alcohol use disorder
- Some suicide attempters develop a behavioral addiction to suicidal behavior

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TITLE: Serum β -endorphin levels is associated with the addiction to suicidal behavior: a pilot study.

Running head: β -endorphin and suicide addiction

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Abstract

The literature provides partial support to the hypothesis that some suicide attempters develop a behavioral addiction to suicidal behavior (SB). We hypothesized that major suicide repeaters (MR) (≥ 5 lifetime suicide attempts) are addicted to suicide attempts as measured with a modified DSM-IV criteria for substance dependence. In this cross-sectional study with 13 psychiatric controls (PC), 55 non-major suicide attempters (NMR), and 9 MR we found that MR are characterized by emotional abuse and neglect, and higher scores using the S-PLE scale. The levels of 8 AM serum ACTH, cortisol and β -endorphin were elevated in all three groups. Serum β -endorphin (pg/mL) was particularly high in PC diagnosed with schizophrenia 220.34 (± 56.30). The level of 8 AM serum β -endorphin raised with an increasing number of criteria for the addiction to SB from 130.31 (± 88.16) (≥ 3 criteria of addiction to SB) to 174.84 (± 114.93) (≥ 6 criteria of addiction to SB) whereas serum ACTH and cortisol did not change. Addicts to SB (≥ 6 criteria) displayed higher serum β -endorphin concentrations than non-addicts (174.84 ± 114.93 vs. 116.93 ± 61.70 , FET $p=0.09$). The present study brings some support to the addictive hypothesis of SB. Our results delineate β -endorphin as a promising biomarker of the addiction to SB, and offer a good basis for future studies testing if buprenorphine can be used to prevent repetitive suicide attempts and non-suicidal-self-injury (NSSI), and the development of an addiction to SB.

1. INTRODUCTION

Most psychiatric patients, and particularly, suicide attempters are at increased suicide risk (Parra-Urbe et al., 2017). Predicting suicide is not possible (Pokorny, 1983), but can be improved by means of better identifying individuals at risk. Unfortunately, the characterization of individuals at risk of suicidal behavior (SB) is not easy (Davis & Schrueder, 1990). Several clinical and biological factors may increase the risk of SB. Unfortunately, there exists huge gaps of knowledge regarding the role of both clinical and biological risk factors.

Regarding the clinical risk factors, major suicide repeaters (MR) (subjects with ≥ 5 lifetime suicide attempts) are a distinct phenotype compared with non-MR (NMR) (subjects with 4 or less lifetime suicide attempts, including single suicide attempters) (H. Blasco-Fontecilla, Artieda-Urrutia, et al., 2014; H. Blasco-Fontecilla et al., 2015; H. Blasco-Fontecilla, Jausent, I., Olié, E., Béziat, S. Guillaume, S., Artieda-Urrutia, P., Malafosse, A., Baca-Garcia, E., de Leon, J., Courtet, P., 2014; Irigoyen-Otinano et al., 2018). MR pose a challenge to clinicians (Kreitman & Casey, 1988), are heavy consumers of health resources and increase the risk of SB (King et al., 1995; Lewinsohn, Rohde, & Seeley, 1994). They represent 10-15% of all suicide attempters (Barnes, 1986; Bille-Brahe et al., 1996; Kreitman & Casey, 1988), and share some features with patients presenting drug and behavioral addictions (H. Blasco-Fontecilla, Jausent, I., Olié, E., Béziat, S. Guillaume, S., Artieda-Urrutia, P., Malafosse, A., Baca-Garcia, E., de Leon, J., Courtet, P., 2014). In 2012 we refined Tullis's theory of suicide addiction by proposing that MR might be addicted to SB (H. Blasco-Fontecilla, 2011). Goodman [6] had previously expanded the concept of addictions from substance to behavioral addictions (Goodman, 1990). This Copernican change allowed the inclusion of gambling, internet use, shopping, exercise, sun-tanning, work, or even love and sex as behavioral addictions (Cassin & von Ranson, 2007; Favazza, 1989; Goodman, 1992; Kourosh, Harrington, & Adinoff, 2010; Reynaud, Karila, Blecha, & Benyamina, 2010; Tantam & Whittaker, 1992; Tao et al., 2010). Behavioral addictions share many characteristics with substance addictions (i.e. tolerance, withdrawal, relapse) (Grant, Brewer, & Potenza, 2006), and common genetic and neurobiological underpinnings (Shaffer et al., 2004). Recently, we presented preliminary clinical evidence supporting the addiction to SB (H. Blasco-Fontecilla, Artieda-Urrutia, et al., 2014). A further step to confirm the addictive hypothesis of SB would be to find a biomarker signature.

As for biological risk factors of SB, the incorporation of biomarkers could increase the specificity and sensitivity of suicide prediction models, thus improving risk assessment (Mann et al., 2006). To date, the most relevant biomarkers for estimating the risk of SB are reduced concentrations of the serotonin metabolite 5-hydroxyindoleacetic acid (5-HIAA) in the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), and non-suppression in the dexamethasone suppression test (DST) (Coryell & Schlessler, 2001; Jokinen, Martensson, Nordstrom, & Nordstrom, 2008). Dysfunctions of the serotonergic system have been consistently reported in studies of mood disorders and SB, and reflect diatheses (trait-dependent risk factors) (Lee & Kim, 2011). Reduced concentrations of 5-HIAA in the CSF have been found in suicide attempters using violent methods (Lester, 1995), and may increase suicide risk by a 4.5-fold (Mann et al., 2006). Non-suppression in the DST reflects hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis dysfunction on stress responses (state-dependent factors) (Lee & Kim, 2011). More recently, serum cholesterol and polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) (Daray, Mann, & Sublette, 2018; Sublette, Hibbeln, Galfalvy, Oquendo, & Mann, 2006), BDNF (Jimenez-Trevino et al., 2017), or SAT1 (Le-Niculescu et al., 2013) have been considered promising biomarkers of SB.

The main objectives of the present study were: 1) to expand our current knowledge on MR and the addictive hypothesis of SB; and 2) to explore if some blood biomarkers (ACTH, cortisol, and β -endorphin) may play a role in the addiction to SB.

We hypothesized that MR: 1) Are addicted to SB as measured with a modified DSM-IV criteria for substance dependence; and 2) display a distinct profile of serum ACTH, cortisol, and β -endorphin. Specifically, we hypothesize that suicide attempters addicted to SB will have higher levels of β -endorphin compared to suicide attempters without an addiction to SB.

2. METHODS

2.1. Sample and procedure

64 suicide attempters (9 MR and 55 NMR) and 13 psychiatric controls (PC) admitted to the emergency department or acute inpatient unit at Puerta de Hierro University Hospital (Majadahonda, Madrid, Spain) were recruited between 1st July 2017 and 15th November 2019. All patients were aged ≥ 18 years, and competent in the Spanish language. All participants signed an informed consent form after the explanation of the study objective

and procedures. The local Ethics Committee approved the study (IRB Number 11.17, 12th June 2017).

All participants were evaluated by interns of Psychiatry and supervised by the principal investigator using a protocol designed to collect socio-demographic and clinical variables following a guideline of suicide assessment (Baca-Garcia, Oquendo, Saiz-Ruiz, Mann, & De Leon, 2006). The patient medical records were reviewed to confirm and complete the information included in the protocol. The main Axis I psychiatric diagnoses were provided by the Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview (MINI) (Sheehan et al., 1998). Axis II disorders were clinically evaluated. Childhood abuse was assessed with the Spanish version of the 28-item Childhood Trauma Questionnaire (CTQ) (D. P. Bernstein, Ahluvalia, Pogge, & Handelsman, 1997). The CTQ is a self-report questionnaire with good reliability and validity for screening diagnoses of sexual, emotional and psychical abuse, and emotional and physical neglect. Each item is rated from 1 (never) to 5 (very often). Scores range from 5 to 25 for each type of trauma. According to Bernstein and Fink thresholds or cut-off scores have been set for each type of trauma at four levels of maltreatment: None, Low, Moderate and Severe. The different cut-offs have been shown to have good specificity and sensibility (D.P. Bernstein & Fink., 1998).

A suicide attempt was defined as "a self-destructive behavior with intent to end one's life independent of resulting damage" (O'Carroll et al., 1996; Silverman, Berman, Sanddal, O'Carroll P, & Joiner, 2007). The protocol included the presence of self-reported non-suicidal-self-injury (NSSI), and of "high volume" repeaters of self-harm (subjects with ≥ 15 lifetime NSSI) (Ness et al., 2016). SB was measured by the Suicide Intent Scale (SIS), the Risk-Rescue Rating Scale (RRRS), the SAD PERSONS, the Self-Injurious Thoughts and Behaviors Interview (SITBI), and the short version of the Personality and Life Event Scale (S-PLE).

The SIS (A. T. Beck, Weissman, Lester, & Trexler, 1974) is the most frequently used scale for measuring suicide intent. The SIS has 15 items rated 0 to 2 (Misson et al., 2010). We used the global score of a shorter version of the SIS loaded by items 4 (act to get help), 7 (note), 12 (seriousness), and 13 (ambivalence about living). This shorter version raised the positive predictive value (PPV) and the area under the curve (AUC) to 19% and 0.82, respectively, in a study evaluating the SIS capability to predicting suicide in a sample of 81 suicide attempters (Stefansson, Nordstrom, & Jokinen, 2012). The

RRRS evaluates suicide risk and rescue expectancies (Weissman & Worden, 1974). High scores are associated with an increased risk of SB. We used 4 questions of the Spanish version of the SITBI (Garcia-Nieto, Blasco-Fontecilla, Paz Yepes, & Baca-Garcia, 2013; Nock, Holmberg, Photos, & Michel, 2007) addressing the reported function of suicide attempts precipitants in a likert scale (0 to 4): *automatic-negative reinforcement* (“To stop bad feelings”), *automatic-positive reinforcement* (“To feel something, because you felt numb or empty”), *social-negative reinforcement* (“To avoid punishment”), *social-positive reinforcement* (“To get attention”). The protocol also included the S-PLE, a 6-item instrument created to improve the identification of individuals at risk of SB (Artieda-Urrutia et al., 2015). The 27 items version of the PLE was constructed using some of the most discriminative variables extracted from different scales frequently used to evaluating SB and sociodemographic factors (age, gender) (H. Blasco-Fontecilla et al., 2012a). The PLE had an AUC of 0.92, an average accuracy of 86.4%, a specificity of 89.6% and a sensitivity of 80.8% in classifying suicide attempters. The S-PLE demonstrated even better accuracy, sensibility, and specificity in classifying suicide attempters than the original version of the PLE (H. Blasco-Fontecilla et al., 2012b).

Finally, we followed the criteria for addiction to SB described elsewhere (H. Blasco-Fontecilla, Artieda-Urrutia, et al., 2014). There are 7 criteria: Criterion 1, tolerance; Criterion 2, withdrawal; Criterion 3, loss of control; Criterion 4, problems in quitting/cutting down; Criterion 5, much time spent using; Criterion 6, substantial reduction in activities; and Criterion 7, adverse physiological/physical consequences. Based on the DSM-IV, the addiction to SB was indicated by the presence of ≥ 3 of these criteria in the last 12 months. Physiological dependence is defined by the presence of either Criterion 1 or 2. These criteria are similar to those used to evaluate the addiction to sun-tanning (Kourosch et al., 2010).

2.2. Blood collection

Serum samples were collected from all patients between 7.30 AM and 8.30 AM. Part of the serum samples were immediately processed to assay ACTH and cortisol levels. Then, blood samples were collected in serum separator tube and left at room temperature for 15–30 min to enable clotting, after which the samples were centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 10 min. Serum was then harvested and stored at -80°C until the assay for β -endorphin levels. Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) were obtained from all blood samples by centrifugation on a Ficoll–Hypaque gradient and frozen in liquid nitrogen (-

196°C) until the assay for β -endorphin levels. β -endorphin levels were measured both at serum and PBMCs. The serum samples of the sample collection were anonymized so that the laboratory personnel were blind to all clinical information.

2.3. Assays of ACTH, cortisol and β -endorphin levels

The levels of 8 AM serum ACTH and cortisol were assayed by chemiluminescence. The level of 8 AM serum β -endorphin (pg/mL) was evaluated using a commercially available enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) Kit [Cloud-Clone Corp (CEA806Hu), range 12.35-1000pg/ml] according to the manufacturer's instructions.

2.4. statistical analyses

Patients were divided into psychiatric controls, MR and non-MR (NMR). Descriptive analysis was performed by means of absolute and relative frequencies for categorical variables and mean (standard deviation), or median (percentiles 25 and 75), minimum and maximum values for numerical variables. Univariable analyses were made with the chi-square or Fisher's exact tests for categorical variables and one-way ANOVA or the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test for numericals (supplementary material, SM).

In order to avoid bias, in some analyses cases (suicide attempters) and controls were matched by sex and age. Only one control per case was suitable. Conditional logistic regression analyses were developed to assess the association between each one of the biomarkers and the group of patients. Boxplots graphs are also shown in SM.

Finally, we explored the discrimination ability of biomarkers to differentiate between addicts to SB and not. We performed a receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC curve) for each one of the parameters and another one for the combination of them. We also explored CTQ item 5 and the S-PLE as predictors of being an addict to SB. Significance level was established at 0.05. Given the limited sample size we also commented on those findings marginally non-significant ($p < 0.10$). Software used has been SPSS v.20 (Macintosh) and Stata/IC v.15.1. (StataCorp. 2017. Stata Statistical Software: Release 15. College Station, TX: StataCorp LLC.).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Sociodemographic features

Compared with PC, suicide attempters were more frequently women but differences did not reach statistical significance (67.2% vs. 46.2%, FET $p = 0.207$). PC were younger than

suicide attempters, but differences were marginally non-significant (33.08 vs. 41.08, $t=-1.754$, $df=76$, $p=0.08$) (see Table 1).

--Please, insert Table 1 about here--

3.2. Personal and familial antecedents

Table 2 displays the clinical features and personal and familial antecedents of PC, NMR, and MR. When compared with NMR, MR displayed differences in: 1) Personal psychiatric antecedents [100% vs. 65.5%, FET $p=.048$, OR=1.25(1.08-1.45)]; 2) Prior psychiatric hospitalization [75% vs. 18.6%, FET $p=.03$, OR=7.93(1.80-34.48)]; 3) Prior history of NSSI [75% vs. 31.1%, FET $p=.042$, OR=4.95(1.10-22.22)]; and 4) Higher probability to be a high volume self-harmer [62.5% vs. 11.1%, FET $p=.004$, OR=7.14(2.04-25)]. MR were less likely diagnosed with Axis I diagnoses (66.7% vs. 89.9%, FET $p=.10$), and more likely diagnosed with Axis II disorder (66.7% vs. 33.3%, FET $p=.007$).

--Please, insert Table 2 about here--

3.3. Child maltreatment and scales measuring SB

Table 3 displays the scores of the different scales measuring child maltreatment and SB. Regarding child maltreatment, 4 items related to emotional maltreatment or neglect (CTQ items 3, 5, 7 and 28) were statistically different in MR compared with NMR and PC. Furthermore, with the exception of the S-PLE scale, none of the scales usually measuring SB were different when comparing MR to NMR and PC.

--Please, insert Table 3--

4. MR status and the addiction to SB

When using the 3 or even the 5 cut-off criteria for diagnosing an addiction to SB, we did not find any statistically significant association. However, there was a clear trend for MR to be more likely diagnosed with an addiction to SB that gained statistical significance with the 6-criteria cut-off point. By using this cut-off point, MR were nearly 5 times more likely diagnosed with an addiction to SB (see Table 4).

--Please, insert Table 4--

5. Serum biomarkers

Table 5, Figure 1 and Figure 2 summarize the values of different blood biomarkers separating by group, Axis I and II diagnoses, presence of NSSI, and addiction to SB (either with the 3 or 6 cut-off criteria). Serum ACTH, cortisol and β -endorphin were elevated in all three groups, particularly in PC. Compared with PC, NMR had statistically significant lower levels of β -endorphin. Regarding Axis I disorders, patients diagnosed with schizophrenia had significantly higher levels of both cortisol and β -endorphin, whereas those patients diagnosed with Substance Use Disorders (SUD) had significantly lower levels of β -endorphin (see Table 5). 5 out of the 7 patients diagnosed with SUD had an alcohol use disorder (AUD).

As for the addiction to SB, serum β -endorphin raised with an increasing number of criteria for the addiction to SB whereas serum ACTH and cortisol not (see Table 5), and serum β -endorphin and the 6 cut-off point criteria for the addiction to SB marginally correlated ($r=2.8$, $p=0.09$). Furthermore, the analyses matching cases (suicide attempters) and controls by sex and age also suggested that β -endorphin increases in subjects addicted to SB (see SM). Unfortunately, one of the suicide attempters included in the study (case 67) died because of the consequences of his suicide attempt (method: shoot gun). This 72-year-old man, with no previous Axis I nor Axis II diagnoses, but recently diagnosed with a cancer, had one of the lowest β -endorphin level of all the sample (22.82 pg/ml).

--Please, insert Table 5, Figure 1, and Figure 2 about here—

Finally, the ROC analysis evaluating the capacity to correctly classify suicide attempters addicted to SB by using β -endorphin and the S-PLE values offered an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.782.

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4. DISCUSSION

The current study expanded current knowledge on clinical phenotypes of suicide attempters, namely, major repeaters (H. Blasco-Fontecilla et al., 2015; Irigoyen-Otinano et al., 2018). More importantly, the trend towards higher serum β -endorphin levels in suicide attempters with ≥ 6 criteria for addiction to SB in comparison to suicide attempters without an addiction to SB is consistent with previous literature suggesting that some suicide attempters are addicted to SB (H. Blasco-Fontecilla, Artieda-Urrutia, et al., 2014; H. Blasco-Fontecilla et al., 2016).

4.1. Clinical outcomes

MR displayed a particular severe psychopathological profile as demonstrated by a higher prevalence of personal psychiatric antecedents, prior psychiatric hospitalization, prior history of NSSI, and a higher probability to be a high-volume self-harmer. This finding is in keeping with literature suggesting that MR have more frequently psychiatric antecedents and a higher risk of become disability pensioners (Irigoyen-Otinano et al., 2018).

Interestingly, 1 item related to emotional maltreatment (CTQ items 3: *People in my family called me things like “stupid”, “lazy”, or “ugly”*) and 3 items related to emotional neglect [CTQ items 5 (*There was someone in my family who helped me feel that I was important or significant*), 7 (*I felt loved*), and 28 (*My family was a source of strength and support*)] were associated with MR status. Childhood victimization has been associated with SB (Brezo et al., 2008) including repetition of suicide attempts (Ystgaard, Hestetun, Loeb, & Mehlum, 2004). Several authors have stressed the role of emotional abuse and neglect on SB (Bach, Molina, Jansen, da Silva, & Souza, 2018; Brown et al., 2018; de Araujo & Lara, 2016). Moreover, we have previously reported an additive effect between very preterm birth and emotional abuse (OR [95% CI] = 4.52 [1.75-11.60]) on the age at first suicide attempt in a sample of 857 adult suicide attempters (H. Blasco-Fontecilla, Jaussent, et al., 2013).

With the exception of the S-PLE scale, none of the scales usually measuring SB differentiated the three groups of patients. The S-PLE has demonstrated to accurately identify suicide attempters (Artieda-Urrutia et al., 2015). In the original study we suggested that a cut-off score above 2.46 accurately classified patients at risk of becoming a suicide attempter. The present study suggests that the 2.46 cut-off point for suicide attempters performs good. However, in a replication study by other group, the authors reported that 1.70 (the cut-off point that we used to classify those mentally healthy) was the best cut-off point for screening purposes (Fernandez-Pelaez et al., 2017). It is also interesting to note that even if the S-PLE was not specifically designed for identifying MR, higher scores on the S-PLE may indicate a risk for major repetition of suicide attempts. This might be explained by the fact that emptiness, the more relevant item of the scale, appears to be a core characteristic of MR (H. Blasco-Fontecilla et al., 2015). This finding is relevant because the S-PLE has several advantages over other scales used to measure suicide risk: 1) The S-PLE just takes one minute to administer; and 2) can be administered to patients with or without SB.

4.2. Major hypotheses

Our results give partial support to our first hypothesis that MR are addicted to SB (H. Blasco-Fontecilla, 2011). By using the 3 and 5 cut-off criteria of addiction to SB (H. Blasco-Fontecilla, Artieda-Urrutia, et al., 2014), results were not statistically significant. However, there was a clear trend for MR to be more likely diagnosed with an addiction to SB that gained statistical significance with the 6 criteria cut-offs. By using this cut-off point, MR were nearly 5 times more likely diagnosed with an addiction to SB. In 1998, Tullis suggested a theory of suicide addiction (Tullis, 1998): individuals addicted to SB should have the presence of multiple addictions, mood disorders, and a history of childhood trauma. Until recently, the only study giving empirical support to this hypothesis was a report of three cases (Mynatt, 2000). In 2014 we reported stronger clinical evidence supporting that major repetition of SB might be another behavioral addiction within Goodman's paradigm (H. Blasco-Fontecilla, Artieda-Urrutia, et al., 2014). More studies replicating that some suicide attempters are addicted to SB warranted.

But the most important finding is that we confirmed our second hypothesis regarding serum biomarkers. As expected, all patients, disregarding the group (PC, NMR or MR) displayed a biomarker profile characterized by elevated serum ACTH, cortisol, and β -endorphin. The hyperactivity of the HPA axis, which controls the secretion of ACTH, cortisol and β -endorphin (Tsigos & Chrousos, 2002), has been associated with depression, violent suicide attempts and suicide completion, among others (Sher, 2006). The diurnal variation of serum β -endorphin peaks at 8 AM (Dent et al., 1981). At this time, the serum β -endorphin concentration is around 50 pg/ml in healthy subjects (Lobstein & Rasmussen, 1991; Sha et al., 2016). We found that β -endorphin concentrations were between 2 and 4 times higher in our patients. Our finding that patients diagnosed with schizophrenia had significantly higher levels of β -endorphin levels is consistent with previous literature. Furthermore, the intermittent but inescapable psychotic symptoms of patients with schizophrenia might parallel the way intermittent forms of inescapable electric foot shock stress activates opioid system in animal models (Schedlowski et al., 1995). On the other hand, patients diagnosed with Substance Use Disorders (SUD), which were mostly diagnosed with an AUD, had significantly lower levels of β -endorphin. Chronic alcohol use decreases brain β -endorphin activity and release (Rasmussen et al., 2000). On the other hand, compared with PC, suicide

attempters displayed lower serum β -endorphin concentrations. This finding can be explained by the cathartic effect of SB (Farberow, 1950), defined as a sudden decrease in the symptoms related to SB following a suicidal crisis (Walker, Joiner, & Rudd, 2001).

More importantly, compared to suicide attempters without and addiction to SB, suicide attempters addicted to SB had higher levels of β -endorphin whereas neither serum ACTH nor cortisol changed. Given that ACTH and β -endorphin are synthesized from a common precursor and secreted concomitantly by the pituitary (Akil et al., 1993), our finding of a higher β -endorphin level without a parallel increase of ACTH levels strongly suggests that β -endorphin is key to explain the addiction to SB. Our findings are in keeping with Beck's "sensitizing" hypothesis (A.T. Beck, 1996). Beck (A.T. Beck, 1996) suggested that previous SB sensitizes SB, such that they become more easily precipitated. Furthermore, the trend for a correlation between serum β -endorphin and the 6-criteria cut-off point is consistent with a study addressing the relationship between plasma β -endorphin concentration and acute stress (parachute jump) in a sample of 47 inexperienced tandem-parachutists. The authors found that "stress-induced β -endorphin secretion was dependent on subjective control attributions", which is similar to our finding of an increased serum β -endorphin concentration correlating with an increasing number of criteria for the addiction to SB.

Finally, the ROC curve merging β -endorphin and the S-PLE values to identify subjects who were addicted to SB offered good values. When using serum β -endorphin and the S-PLE scale alone, the AUC of the ROC curves offered values lower than 0.75. ROC curves with an AUC lower than 0.75 are not clinically useful (Fan, Upadhye, & Worster, 2006). However, by combining β -endorphin and the S-PLE scale, the AUC was higher than 0.75, and therefore, clinically useful. Thus, the combination of biological and clinical risk factors associated with SB appears to be a good strategy to improve the predictive capacity of explanatory SB models (H. Blasco-Fontecilla, Lopez-Castroman, Giner, Baca-Garcia, & Oquendo, 2013; Le-Niculescu et al., 2013).

4.3. Strengths and limitations

The major strength of the current study is the evaluation of different serum biomarkers in similar conditions, thus making comparable data between PC and suicide attempters. In this paper, we used plasma β -endorphin concentrations (Panerai et al., 2002). The serum

β -endorphin level may not reflect exactly its central activity (Bidari, Ghavidel-Parsa, Rajabi, Sanaei, & Toutounchi, 2016). However, recent literature supports a link between plasma and CSF β -endorphin levels (Adeodu, Olorunmoteni, Oseni, & Obuotor, 2018).

The current study suffers from the usual limitations of retrospective studies (Hjelmeland, 1996). The small sample size hampered our capability to match by age and sex the different groups for the most relevant analyses, and limited our capacity to find some statistically significant differences. However, some of the trends commented have a strong clinical value. Moreover, the lack of statistical power prevented us to control for potential confounders. However, we analyzed if there were differences regarding the use of different drugs during the index episode in all three groups, and we found no statistically significant differences. Another limitation is that single attempters and “minor repeaters” were considered into a single category (NMR) in order to gain statistical power. As explained elsewhere, it is very unlikely that a single attempter becomes a MR (H. Blasco-Fontecilla, Jaussent, et al., 2014). Accordingly, the statistically significant differences reported here characterize MR.

4.4. Conclusions

The search for a biological marker of suicide risk is a long-standing pursuit of clinical psychiatry. The present study gives preliminary support to the role of β -endorphins in the addiction to SB. Our results delineate β -endorphin as a promising biomarker of the addiction to SB, and offer a good basis for future studies testing if buprenorphine can be used to prevent repetitive suicide attempts and NSSI, and the development of an addiction to SB. Buprenorphine, a potent κ -opioid antagonist and μ -opioid partial agonist, appears to be beneficial in the treatment of NSSI, suicidal ideation and SB (Norelli, Smith, Sher, & Blackwood, 2013; Yovell et al., 2016), but evidence is lacking on repetitive SB.

Furthermore, the combination of β -endorphins and the S-PLE scale may have potential for screening the risk of suicide attempters to become addicts to SB. Moreover, MR are a subgroup of suicide attempters who present a unique profile characterized by a higher psychiatric load, a history of emotional abuse and neglect, and an increased risk to become addicted to SB. However, the concept of major suicide repetition and the addiction to SB are not synonymous and should not be used interchangeably. Future studies of MR and/or addicts to SB may establish specific preventive plans for these patients.

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Table 1: Sociodemographic features (N=77)

	PC n (%)	NMR n (%)	MR n (%)	Total n (%)	χ^2	df	p-value
Sex					2.57	2	.27
Female	6 (46.2)	36 (65.5)	7 (77.8)	49 (63.6)			
Living with					12.843	6	.046
Alone	0 (0.0)	12 (21.8)	3 (33.3)	15 (19.7)			
Friends	3 (25)	2 (3.6)	1 (11.1)	6 (7.9)			
With partner	3 (25)	26 (47.3)	2 (22.2)	31 (40.8)			
Family of origin	6 (50)	16 (27.3)	3 (33.3)	25 (31.6)			
Nationality					0.709	2	0.702
Spanish	9 (69.2)	44 (80)	7 (77.8)	60 (77.9)			
Other	4 (30.8)	11 (20)	2 (22.2)	17 (21.1)			
Socioeconomic level (Euros/month)					7.21	8	.514
<500	2 (33.3)	4 (10.8)	1 (20.0)	7 (14.6)			
500-1500	0 (0)	9 (24.3)	2 (40.0)	11 (22.9)			
1500-2000	1 (16.7)	12 (32.4)	0 (0)	13 (27.1)			
2000-2500	2 (33.3)	5 (13.5)	1 (20.0)	8 (16.7)			
> 2500	1 (16.7)	7 (18.9)	1 (20.0)	9 (18.8)			
Age	Mean (Sd)	Mean (Sd)	Mean (Sd)	Mean (Sd)	F	df	p-value
	33.08 (15.10)	41.80 (15.65)	37.67 (10.88)	39.84 (15.29)	1.85	2	.164

PC: Psychiatric controls who have no history of previous suicide attempts; NMR: Non-major repeaters; MR: Major repeaters

Table 2: Clinical features and personal and familial antecedents.

	PC n (%)	NMR n (%)	MR n (%)	TOTAL n (%)	χ^2	df	p-value
Familial antecedents of mental disorders	2 (100)	29 (60.4)	5 (62.5)	44 (66.7)	5.906	2	.052
Familial antecedents of SB	2 (16.7)	16 (30.8)	2 (25.0)	20 (27.8)	1.001	2	.606
Medical antecedents	2 (15.45)	16 (29.1)	4 (44.4)	22 (28.6)	2.226	2	.329
Psychiatric antecedents	11 (84.6)	36 (65.5)	9 (100)	56 (72.7)	5.768	2	.056
Previous psychiatric hospitalization	4 (50)	8 (18.6)	6 (75)	18 (30.5)	11.77	2	.003
Lifetime tobacco-alcohol-drug use	9 (69.2)	40 (72.7)	7 (77.8)	56 (72.7)	.196	2	.907
History of past NSSI	3 (30)	14 (31.1)	6 (75)	23 (36.5)	5.862	2	.053
High volume NSSI (>15 NSSI lifetime)	2 (20)	5 (11.1)	5 (62.5)	12 (19)	11.640	2	.003
Axis I disorder (index episode)	11 (84.6)	42 (89.4)	6 (66.7)	59 (85.5)	6.265	2	0.04
Main Axis I Diagnosis (index episode)					22.49	18	.211
Generalized Anxiety Disorder	0 (0)	2 (4.9)	0 (0)	2 (3.5)			
Bipolar disorder	1 (9.1)	1 (2.4)	1 (20)	3 (5.2)			
Major Depressive Disorder	2 (18.2)	9 (22)	1 (20)	12 (21.1)			
Psychotic disorder (current)	3 (27.3)	1 (2.4)	1 (20)	5 (8.8)			
Substance use disorder	1 (9.1)	4 (9.8)	2 (40)	7 (12.3)			
Adjustment disorder	3 (27.3)	20 (48.8)	0 (0)	24 (40.4)			
Axis II disorder (Yes) (index episode)	6 (46.2)	16 (33.3)	6 (66.7)	28 (40)	3.791	2	.153
Previous psychiatric hospitalizations (number)	Mean (Sd) 2 (.82)	Mean (Sd) .59 (1.2)	Mean (Sd) 3.62 (3.38)	Mean (Sd) 1.32 (2.10)	F 9.75	df 2	p-value <.001

PC: Psychiatric controls who have no history of previous suicide attempts; NMR: Non-major repeaters; MR: Major repeaters; Non suicidal self-injuries (NSSI)

Table 3: Scales evaluating child maltreatment and suicidal behavior.

	PC Mean (Sd)	NMR Mean (Sd)	MR Mean (Sd)	TOTAL Mean (Sd)	F	df	p-value
CTQ Item 3 (People in my family called me things like “stupid”, “lazy”, or “ugly”) (n=50)	.71 (.95)	.97 (1.42)	2.57 (1.39)	1.16 (1.46)	4.428	2	.017
CTQ Item 5 (« There was someone in my family who helped me feel that I was important or significant ») (n=49)	3.43 (.97)	2.40 (1.57)	1.29 (1.70)	2.39 (1.60)	3.441	2	.004
CTQ Item 7 (« I felt loved») (n=50)	3.71 (.76)	3.06 (1.35)	1.71 (1.70)	2.96 (1.43)	4.208	2	.021
CTQ Item 15 (« I believe that I was physically abused) (n=49)	0 (0)	.71 (1.32)	1.57 (1.81)	.73 (1.35)	2.536	2	.090
CTQ Item 21 (« Someone threatened to hurt me or tell lies about me unless I did something sexual with them ») (n=50)	.57 (.97)	.08 (.37)	.29 (.76)	.18 (.56)	2.516	2	.092
CTQ Item 23 (« Someone tried to make me do sexual things or watch sexual things ») (n=50)	.57 (.97)	3.06 (1.19)	1.33 (1.75)	2.86 (1.41)	2.644	2	.082
CTQ Item 28 (« My family was a source of strength and support) (n=49)	3.14 (1.57)	3.06 (1.19)	1.33 (1.75)	2.86 (1.41)	4.573	2	.015
S-PLE score (n=56)	2.22 (.80)	2.59 (.44)	2.94 (.45)	2.58 (.52)	3.587	2	.035
		MSA Mean (Sd)	MR Mean (Sd)	TOTAL Mean (Sd)	t	df	p-value
Beck SIS short version (n=43) (Items 4 + 7 +12 +13)		3.33 (2.58)	2.14 (1.86)	3.14 (2.50)	1.156	41	.254
WWS (Global score) (n=42)		8.89 (1.84)	8.83 (1.47)	8.88 (1.78)	.070	40	.945
SAD PERSONS (n=43)		2.91 (3.28)	3.28 (1.70)	2.97 (1.42)	-.624	41	.536
Reported function (0-4 scale) (n=42)		Mean (Sd)	Mean (Sd)	Mean (Sd)			
Automatic negative reinforcement		3.11 (1.32)	4 (0)	3.26 (1.25)	-1.753	40	.087
Automatic positive reinforcement		2.15 (1.78)	2.71 (1.89)	2.24 (1.78)	-.761	39	.451
Social negative reinforcement		2.26 (1.80)	3.43 (1.13)	2.46 (1.74)	-1.638	39	.110
Social positive reinforcement		1.31 (1.71)	1 (1.73)	1.26 (1.69)	.443	40	.660
Criteria for addiction to SB (0-7 criteria) (n=38)		1.54 (2.06)	4.14 (2.67)	2.02 (2.37)	-2.849	36	.007

PC: Psychiatric controls who have no history of previous suicide attempts; NMR: Non-major repeaters; MR: Major repeaters; Automatic negative reinforcement: “To stop bad feelings”; Automatic positive reinforcement: “To feel something, because you felt numb or empty”; Social negative reinforcement: “To avoid doing something you don’t want to do”; Social positive reinforcement: “To communicate with someone or get his/her attention”.

Table 4. MR and addiction to SB.

Variables	Number of suicide attempts					
	n	%	n	%	OR [95% CI]	p-value
	<5 (NMR) N=31		≥5 (MR) N=7			
Addiction to SB (≥ 3 criteria)						
No	21	87.5	3	12.5		0.387
Yes	10	71.4	4	28.6		
Addiction to SB (≥ 5 criteria)						
No	27	87.1	4	12.9		0.101
Yes	4	57.1	3	42.9		
Addiction to SB (≥ 6 criteria)						
No	29	87.9	4	12.1	1	0.035
Yes	2	40	3	60	4.95 [1.54;15.87]	

Table 5. Blood biomarkers regarding Axis I and II diagnoses.

GROUP	ACTH Mean (Sd)	Cortisol Mean (Sd)	B-endorphin Mean (Sd)	t	df	p-value
NMR (n=55)	23.23 (18.93)	15.48 (7.33)	108.45 (66.86)	1.284	63	.204 (ACTH)
				.536	62	.229 (Cortisol)
				.033	66	.033 (B-endorphin)
MR (n=9)	23.32 (10.82)	15.08 (8.69)	124.85 (94.13)	.991	20	.334 (ACTH)
				.947	20	.355 (Cortisol)
				.785	20	.442 (B-endorphin)
PC* (n=13)	30.94 (21.1)	18.22 (6.84)	158.25 (100.71)			
AXIS I DISORDERS						
Schizophrenia (n=5)	39.2 (25.57)	26.09 (6.21)	220.34 (56.30)	1.275	25	.214 (ACTH)
				2.910	25	.007 (Cortisol)
				2.395	25	.024 (B-endorphin)
MDD (n=13)	21.45 (17)	13.90 (8.04)	103.16 (53.87)	-.685	33	.498 (ACTH)
				-.731	32	.470 (Cortisol)
				-.967	32	.340 (B-endorphin)
SUD* (n=7)	27.21 (25.32)	15.49 (8.64)	58.71 (33.59)	.132	27	.896 (ACTH)
				-.115	27	.910 (Cortisol)
				-3.208	27	.040 (B-endorphin)
Adaptive disorder* (n=22)	25.99 (19.96)	15.87 (7.24)	127.76 (81.51)			
AXIS II DISORDERS						
No (n=42)	23.22 (17.92)	15.72 (7.09)	132.38 (81.72)			
Yes (n=28)	29.17 (19.83)	17.43 (7.65)	96.1 (65.41)	-1.290	67	.202 (ACTH)
				-.940	66	.351 (Cortisol)
				1.965	68	.053 (B-endorphin)
Addition to SB (≥ 3 criteria)						
No (n=24)	21.92 (18.05)	16.17 (8.53)	121.18 (61.66)			
Yes (n=14)	25.86 (19.38)	13.29 (7.54)	130.31 (88.16)	-.613	33	.544 (ACTH)
				1.022	33	.314 (Cortisol)
				-.375	36	.710 (B-endorphin)
Addition to SB (≥ 6 criteria)						
No (n=33)	23.22 (19.78)	15.04 (8.47)	116.93 (61.70)			
Yes (n=5)	25.18 (6.55)	14.86 (6.82)	174.84 (114.93)	-.217	33	.830 (ACTH)
				.242	33	.963 (Cortisol)
				-.1.733	36	.092 (B-endorphin)

*Reference group

Figure 1. Blood biomarkers (ACTH, Cortisol, and β -endorphin).

Figure 2. Distribution of β -endorphin (pg/ml) regarding group (Psychiatric controls, PC; Non-major repeaters, NMR; and Major Repeaters, MR).

Figure 3. Classification of patients addicted to SB using ROC Curves with the combined S-PLE and serum β -endorphin.

AUTHOR DISCLOSURE

ROLE OF THE FUNDING SOURCE

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AUTHOR DISCLOSURE

CONTRIBUTORS

HBF designed the study and wrote the protocol. JHH, EGB, and TPL recruited all patients and filled-out the protocols. HBF managed the literature searches. EDN and EHA managed ACTH and beta-endorphin analyses. IG and JJM provide support on beta-endorphin management and analyses. MGL, SRG and ASL processed the samples at the biobank. HBF undertook the statistical analysis, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. All authors contributed to and have approved the final manuscript.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

In the last two years, Dr. Hilario Blasco-Fontecilla has received lecture fees from AB-Biotics, Rovi, Praxis, and Shire. He has been paid by Praxis for the elaboration of an article. He was the recipient of a FIPSE Grant. He is involved in two clinical trials (ESKETINSUI2002, and NEWROFEED). The remaining authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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